

The Trial of Jesus in the Fourth Gospel (John 18:28-40)

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Abstract

This article focused primarily on the trial of Jesus in the Fourth Gospel (John 18:28-40). He was arrested in the garden by the temple Jewish police in collaboration with the Roman soldiers (John 18:12). He was brought first to Annas who was the Father-in-law for informal trial (John 19:24), then they led him from the house of Caiaphas who was the High Priest that year to the Praetorium for the formal trial (John 18:28-40).

Of what crime Jesus was accused before Pilate by the high priests? In Matthew and Mark, Pilate's question was not fully explained, for it was said that they handed him over to Pilate (Matt 27:2//Mark 15:1). In John, there were no written charges instead Jesus was presented as the evil doer (John 18:29). Since the charges raised by officials reflected particular Jewish concerns regarding their scripture and laws, Pilate instructed them to judge Jesus according to their law (John 18:31).

But the Jews offered Pilate a reason why he must be involved: they were seeking a death sentence, and they lacked the authority to exercise it. In the same line, they acknowledged Rome's greater authority when they admitted that they were not permitted to put anyone to death. They also acknowledged Rome's ultimate authority over Jesus: whether he lived or died will be decided by the Roman laws, not by the Jewish laws. Finally Jesus was condemned to death unjustly. Although, in the beginning, there were fair proceedings of the trial of Jesus, at the end of it, there were no judgment; instead Pilate handed over him to be crucified by Roman soldiers. Three times, Pilate declared Jesus to be innocent but unfortunately, he was unable to stand for what he had confirmed.

Keywords: *Trial, Jesus, Pilate, The Jews, Crucifixion.*

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Introduction

The story of the passion and death of Jesus in the Fourth Gospel was traditionally understood to start from arrest of Jesus in the garden (John 18:12), trial by the Jews' officials (John 18:13, 19-24), Pilate (John 18:28-40), crucifixion, death and his burial (John 19:38-42). This article focused mainly

on the trial of Jesus by Roman authority (John 18:28-40). Based on the exegetical analysis of the text, the article intended to demonstrate on how the trial of Jesus was conducted by Pilate. Did he really follow right procedures in handling the case of Jesus?

The article has two main parts: the first part mainly concentrated on the scriptural passages as point of references when trying to establish on how the trial of Jesus was handled by Pontius Pilate. The four Gospels were consulted although the main interest was in particular on the Fourth Gospel. The second part treated his trial in the light of the Roman laws: its aim intended to find if Roman procedures were followed. The trial was completed and the judgment given by Pilate was fair and reasonable. Besides, a conclusion given at the end of this work depended so much on the findings that arose from the research.

Methods

The method employed in this article was narrative analysis.

Jesus' Trial before Pilate (John 18:28-40)

All four Gospels agreed that Jesus was handed over to Pilate by the Jewish priestly leaders, though only John recorded the presence of Roman troops at Jesus' arrest, a detail which suggested prior Roman involvement (Bock, 2010; Rensberger, 1984). From this point, however, the Gospels differed enormously in terms of the precise sequence of events, the details of Jesus' trial, and Pilate's attitude towards both Jesus and his Jewish opponents (Bond, 2010). The trial before Pilate, the Roman authority was only the trial scene in John, and the accusations against Jesus were the political one (Rensberger, 2015). This was unique to John and seemed to reverse the common Christian practice of defending the Roman Empire and placing the blame on the Jews (Doohan, 1988). The Synoptic tradition had already used the trial of Jesus before Pilate and the sign of the cross to proclaim Jesus as "king" (cf. Mark 15:2, 9, 12, 18, 26, 32; Matt 27:11, 29, 37, 42; Luke 23:2, 3, 27, 38).

In the Gospel of Mark, Jesus was never called a "king" until he stood before Pilate on the way to the cross, yet from within the space of thirty verses, he was called "king" six times: three times by Pilate (Mark 15:2, 9, 12), twice by mockers just before and just after the crucifixion (Mark 15:18, 32) and once by the inscription over his cross (Mark 15:26).

But John reported far more details of this trial before Pilate than did the three Gospels. In Johannine story, the theme of Jesus' royal status dominated the interrogation of Jesus by Pilate (cf. 18:33, 37, 39; 19:3, 12, 14, 15) and continued into the scene of the crucifixion (cf. 19:19, 21).

The "trial" is marked by an introduction (John 18:28) seven brief scenes that took place either inside or outside the *Praetorium* (John 18:29-32, 33-38a, 38b-40; 19:1-3, 4-7, 8-11, 12-15), and a conclusion (John 19:16a). The Evangelist used the verbs of motion to show that Pilate and or Jesus came in or went out (evxh/lqen). There were two "trials" in progress: one followed from encounter between the Roman authority of Pilate and "the Jews" (cf. John 18:29-32, 38b-40; 19:5-7, 12-15) and encountered between Pilate and Jesus (cf. John 18:33-38a; 19:8-11).

The episode was set at the *Praetorium*, Pilate's headquarters in Jerusalem and all characters were introduced: Jesus, Pilate and the Jewish leaders (verse 28). In the first scene, Jesus bound was led from house of Caiaphas to the *Praetorium*. It was early in the Morning -prwi< (John 18:28). Verse 29 introduced Pilate without any narrative explanation of his identity. John could assume his readers were familiar with a name that even appeared in one of the New Testament 'creeds' (1Tim 6:13). The action moved from outside to the inside, as Pilate moved between the Jews, who

remained outside the *Praetorium*, and Jesus, who had been taken into the *Praetorium* (Thompson, 2015). Pilate, the judge was compelled to make movements in and out because the Jewish leaders refused to come inside for fear of defilement (John 18:28), and at the same time had to interrogate Jesus who had been handed over to him for crime against the state (Brown–Moloney, 2017). The narrator offered the reason for the Jews’ remaining outside in order that they might not become defiled but might eat the Passover (John 18:28). It might well be that the ritual defilement to be avoided was contact with a corpse, which carried seven-day contamination, and that in view were laws found later in the Mishnah in which Gentiles houses were treated as unclean because Gentiles sometimes buried corpses in or underneath them, particularly premature babies or fetuses (Lincoln, 2005). As “the Jews” struggled to maintain their ritual purity on the occasion of Passover (cf. John 11:55-57), they sought the death of Lamb of God (Moloney, 1998).

Pilate, the Roman governor came out to meet them and asked them, “What accusation did you bring against this man?” (John 18:29). In essence, Pilate’s question was a request for a charge (Keener, 2003). Thus the formal trial had begun officially in contrast to the informal trial conducted by the high priest Annas (John 18:19). The fact that Roman troops were used at arrest in verses 3, 12) proved that the Jewish authorities had communicated something of this case to Pilate in advance. They expected Pilate to confirm their judgment and order death sentence by crucifixion; instead he ordered a fresh hearing in his presence (Carson, 1991). Initially, in response to Pilate’s question, the Jews were depicted as not having a specific charge to bring against Jesus. He was simply represented in general terms as an evildoer (cf. Mark 15:14 par.), although in verse 33 it was presupposed that the charge was that Jesus claimed to be the King of Jews, that he was a political subversive with royal pretensions (Schnabel, 2017).

It was clear that Jesus’ accusers were not looking for a fair trial that followed the proper legal process. Mark and Matthew gave no explanation of the charges, Luke indicated that they were political and John explained that they were religious (Wilson, 1970). They wanted the Roman governor to rubber-stamp the sentence that had already passed. No charges were mentioned. In John’s Gospel, it was even more puzzling in that Pilate asked them, “What charge do you bring against this man?” (v. 29) and they offered no specific charges, merely claiming that he had done evil. Elsewhere Jesus’ opponents charged that he was (i) a violator of the Sabbath and the law, a “sinner” (John 5:18; 9:14-16, 24); (ii) a blasphemer (John 5:17-18; 8:58; 10:24-38; 19:7); (iii) a false teacher, who led the people astray (John 7:12; 45-49; 18:19-24 and (iv) a threat to the survival of the Jewish people and their temple (Thompson, 2015).

But the Jews offered Pilate a reason why he must be involved: they were seeking a death sentence, and they lacked the authority to carry it. If Jesus had been put to death by the Sanhedrin, stoning would have been the likely mode of execution, (O’day–Hysten, 2006, since it was the penalty specified in the Old Testament for blasphemy, (Cf. Leviticus 24:16; cf. John 10:33; Acts 7:57-58; *m. Sanh.* 7:4; 9:3) and most common charge against Jesus in John. Other forms of capital punishment sanctioned by mishnaic were burning, beheading and strangling (*m. Sanh.* 7.1, Köstenberger, 2007; Hassner, 2003). To be clear and specific, Jesus will be put to death by crucifixion, which was a Roman rather than a Jewish form of execution (Klink, 2016). The Jewish authorities acknowledged that they needed the Romans in order to put Jesus to death, and eventually the Romans complied (Thompson, 2015).

On three occasions in the earlier narrative they had claimed that the law convicted Jesus blasphemy and tried to kill him (John 5:18; 8:59; 10:30). These earlier attempts to carry out a death sentence on Jesus on the basis of a religious charge under the law had prevented them from doing, and so, as emerged from the dialogue, his opponents were forced to bring a political charge and involved the Romans in order to convict Jesus of a capital offence (Lincoln, 2005, 461). The Evangelist’s comment was that all this only brought about the fulfillment of Jesus’ own words indicating the

kind of death he was to die (John 12:32). So, in this light, “the Jews” transference of his case to Pilate was simply the means of enabling his words to be fulfilled (John 18:32).

The second scene moved inside the *Praetorium*: Pilate went back into *Praetorium*. The trial was a confrontation between two kingdoms in their extreme form: the kingdom of the truth for which Jesus died to save others, and irreligious world of Pilate who killed in order to save himself (Mullinis, 2003). This scene provided a dialogue between Pilate and Jesus about the fact and the nature of his kingship (John 18:36-37). To Pilate’s question, “Are you the king of the Jews?” (John 18:33), suggested he had been told that Jesus was the leader of a rebellion against Roman authority, a charge that was important enough to force Pilate to take the case seriously (Adeyemo, 2006, Long, 1997). And anyone who claimed himself of being the King of Jews was high treason and implied rebellion against the Roman Emperor, since Judea was a province of his empire (Grant, 1977). Pilate’s question “Are you the King of Jews?” was exactly the same question, words for words, that he asked in all four Gospels (compare Matt 27:11//Mark 15:2//Luke 23:3, leaving a person to wonder where the tittle came from, and where Pilate got the idea that this was Jesus what he might be claiming. This was a dangerous question and it was purely a political question.

In each Gospel, the question began with emphatic Greek **Su..** (You) “Are you a King of the Jews?” This suggested that Pilate could well have been astonished that Jesus was claiming such tittle (Borchert, 1996). Jesus hardly had an army, and he certainly had not led an uprising against Romans as a rebel king might have been tempted to do. Pilate’s question intended to find out whether or not Jesus constituted a political threat to Roman power (Köstenberger, 2007). In Mark’s Gospel the nature of Christ kingship was not defined, as it was in John 18:36. Jesus’s response to Pilate’s question “Do you ask this on your own, or did others tell you about me?” (John 18:34). Jesus’ response to Pilate (v. 34) set the tone of the trial in two ways: first Jesus answered Pilate with his own question, turning down the tables and raising the possibility that it was really Jesus who was the judge at the trial (O’day–Hysten, 2006). A second and related effect of this question was to raise uncertainty about Pilate to act on his own. Pilate’s defense question, “I am not a Jew, am I?” (John 18:35), portrayed himself on trial. He dissociated himself from the Jews, yet in the narrative, he allied himself more and more closely with the wishes of the Jews (Swartley, 2013).

Jesus was fully aware that the title “King of the Jews” had more than one definition, especially given the different cultural, political and religious backgrounds of the Jews and Romans. Hence, he could not simply answer Pilate’s question; he must first defined the sense in which he was and he was not (John 18:36). Jesus’ ability to stand as a witness in his own trial had also been seen in John’s way Jesus gave an enigmatic answer, “You say that I am a king”- *su. le,geij o[ti basileu,j eivmi* (John 18:37b). The answer given by Jesus seemed to carry an ambiguous meaning (Schwiebert, 2017). It was neither a denial nor an affirmation. It might have two meanings, “You say that I am a king, I did not say” or “You say rightly that I am a king” (Maniparampil, 2004; Boring, 2006). Jesus accepted to be the king, and he was born for that purpose but his kingdom had nothing to interfere with the worldly kingdom. He was born as the king and he came into the world to bear witness to the truth and everyone who was of the Truth heard his voice (verse 37). From this perspective, Pilate stood as character who presented a power which did not witness the truth. When Pilate asked him, “What have you done?” The reader knew that Jesus’ whole life ministry had been a revelation of, and witness to the truth, a revelation of the Father and his grace (faithful loving and kindness) and truth (John 5:31, 36 and in John 8:14). The reader perceived that Jesus was “the Truth” (John 14:6). Those who “belonged to the Truth (v. 37), who therefore belonged to Jesus, listened to his voice (see John 10:4, 16). When Pilate heard this statement, he asked Jesus what was the truth? (John 18:38). Pilate’s question demonstrated that he did not understand who Jesus was: he did not recognize the Truth that stood in front of him. If Pilate really belonged to the Truth, he would have listened to Jesus (John 18:37).

Pilate did not witness to the truth and justice that sprung from it. He proclaimed the innocence of Jesus and immediately undermined his own judgment. The weakness of supreme human power without principle and moral courage was revealed (Mullinis, 1989). The governor was ruled by aggravation of fear of the governed. The truth he had spoken with his lips was denied by his actions. He was unable to commit himself to the truth.

He went out again to the Jews (verse 38a) and the reason Pilate went back to the Jewish leaders was to tell them, “I find no basis for a charge against him (John 18:38b). This was a public statement, not simply a private communication to those who brought Jesus to him. I find no crime in this man (John 18:38), he said. Having found Jesus’ innocence, Pilate suggested that he released him, as it was a custom for a prisoner to be released at Passover time (verse 39). He employed the custom of releasing a political prisoner at Passover; he offered the crowd a choice between Jesus Barabbas, a notorious criminal or Jesus who is called the Messiah (Matt 27:17). It was interesting to note that outside of the New Testament no historical evidence might be found for this practice of releasing criminals in Passover, but the argument given by Matthew here was more of theological than historical (Luz, 2005; Porter, 1995; Kee –Young–Froehlich, 1965).

Although Barabbas’ activities in the Synoptic Gospels might be described as those of a bandit, for John, the particular word “bandit”(lh|sth,j) had been used earlier in the Gospel,(John 10:1) and that earlier usage and context were evoked here. The bandit was the one who entered the sheepfold by another way, to whom the sheep would not listen (John 10:1, 8). He gave them choice between “the king of Jews” or Barabbas. Barabbas was under arrest for a political sedition (Loader, 2017). In Matthew’s Gospel, he was known as Jesus Barabbas - ÎVIhsou/n to.nÐ Barabba/n (Matt 27:17). The choice of Barabbas robbed Jesus’ life, the Jews of their heritage and Pilate of his authority (Mullinis, 2003).

But the trial was not over yet, and Pilate did not stand by what he knew to be the truth about Jesus. While Pilate did not expect that Jesus held the answer to his question, the reader knew he did. In the end there was no sentence, but a capitulation on the part of the governor, who abandoned Jesus “to please the crowd” (Légasse, 1997). But Jesus’ trial went through a completely new cycle; hence the verdict and sentence were postponed (Neyrey, 2007).

The Roman Procedure on the Trial of Jesus

Pilate was a Roman governor of the province of Judea, a minor official but his name became most famous and known around the world because of Jesus suffered under Pontius Pilate, was crucified, died and buried (Long, 1997). According to Josephus, Pilate as the governor had the power of life and death over all the inhabitants of his province (Garland, 2011; Hare, 1996; Wilson, 1970). In Judea at the time of Jesus, sentencing to crucifixion and execution were entirely in the hands of the Roman authorities (Brandenburger, 1982; Koester, 2007). Roman governors had exclusive jurisdiction in capital cases, without any limitations on their *coercitio* (power to correct and enforce), especially when law and order needed to be maintained against troublemakers (Schnabel, 2017).

Penal *coercitio* measures included imposition of fines, seizing of property, corporal punishment and capital punishment (Schnabel, 2017). In the case of provincials who did not have Roman citizenship, the governors had the authority to impose penal *coercitio* measure at their discretion. Pilate, as the prefect of Judea, had the sole authority to acquit or to condemn, and to determine the sentence. In John 19:10, Pilate said to Jesus “Do you know that I have power to release, power to crucify you?” Pilate’s question differed from Jesus’ answer. In reality, Pilate had no authority over Jesus, unless was given from above (cf. John 19:11). Three times, he declared Jesus’ guiltless but he was unable to stand for the truth. In this case the Jews could not act apart from Pilate’s approval; as they themselves acknowledged, they could not put Jesus to death (John 18:31b). The

evidence from the *titulus* which described Jesus as King of the Jews indicated clearly that Jesus was executed by Roman authorities for sedition (Schnabel, 2017). This charge was too embarrassing for Christian to have invented (Bock, 2010).

With regard to the procedure followed by Romans the following may be said. As with the Greeks and probably throughout the East, the freemen with Roman citizenship were exempted from crucifixion up to the early imperial period. In this case, the crucifixion was inflicted on slaves, (Cook, 2008; Jensen, 2017; Black, 2011) foreigners and inhabitants of foreign provinces (Thompson, 2015). As a rule, crucifixion was inflicted on slaves only in cases of serious crimes. It was significant that this form of capital punishment was instituted primarily for offences against state, such as treason that was potentially dangerous to security of the state (Viladesau, 2006).

A Roman judicial process differed significantly from Jewish trial. The latter was based on the testimony of witnesses (an example is *Sms* 28-64); the former like that of the Greeks, was based on the accusation and the ability of the accused to speak in own defense (a famous example is the apology of Socrates). In the case of Jesus, the roles in the trial were thus clear. The chief priests were the accusers, Jesus was the accused and Pilate was the judge. Jesus had no rights in the Roman court because he was not a Roman citizen. The judge heard accusations (Luke 23:2; John 18:29), discerned the facts and passed the judgment. The Romans dealt with royal pretenders harshly (Culpepper, 2021). The result of the trial was clear. The so called trial before Pilate was hardly properly so described. Although the Jewish leaders brought accusations against Jesus (which he refused to answer) sentence was never passed. Jesus was condemned to die by means of the Roman punishment of crucifixion (as an expression of Roman *coercitio*. A trial did take place before Pilate, therefore, who was probably a judge, the trial end in an appropriate judgment (Becker, 1998). Instead Pilate decided to release Jesus under the Passover amnesty, this implied that he had been convicted already, and finally handed him over to be crucified, a law that never existed (Hooker, 1991).

Jesus was tried before the Sanhedrin on the charge of blasphemy. This was religious offense of most serious nature (Collins, 1996). But when he was led before Pilate, this charge was abandoned and that of high treason against Rome was substituted (Chandler, 2012). It might be asked why the Sanhedrists did not maintain the same charges before Pilate that they themselves had considered before their own tribunal. They changed the charge because blasphemy was not an offense against Roman law, and Roman judges would generally assume cognizance of no charges (Judge, 2003.) Instead they began to accuse him saying “We found this fellow perverting the nation, and forbidding to give tribute to Caesar, saying that he himself is Christ, a king” (Luke 23:2).

To forbid paying tribute to Caesar in Judea was a form of treason, not only because it was an open defiance of the law of Roman state, but also because it was a direct denial of Roman sovereignty in Palestine. Finally the last charge was that he claimed to be “Christ a King. Again this was the last and greatest of the charges. By this he was deliberately accused of high treason against Caesar, the gravest offense known in the Roman law (Chandler, 2012). Such accusation could not be ignored by Pilate who was a loyal depute of Tiberius Caesar.

Did Pilate act in strict obedience to the requirements of Roman laws in trying Jesus? With regard to this matter, some writers were divided in their opinions. There were those who believed that the trial of Jesus before Roman official did not follow the proper procedures while the others believed that the New Testaments records, though meager in details exhibit all the essential elements of an ordinary trial whether conducted in ancient or modern times (Chandler, 2012).

Those who supported the presence of the proper proceedings of the trial of Jesus, they highlighted the following points: Pilate went out (verse 29a). His question: what charges did you bring against this man? This question was keenly suggestive of the presence of a judge and of the beginning of

a solemn judicial proceeding. Every word rang with Roman authority and administrative capacity. The suggestion was also prominent that accusation was more important element in Roman criminal trials than inquisition (Chandler, 2012). The second point was the Examination, or *Interrogatio*: “Are you the king of Jews?” This kind of question suggested that this was the accusation on the basis of which Jesus has been handed over: he was accused of claiming to be a king. The interrogation gave the impression of a judicial inquiry, touching a matter involving the question of high treason, the charge against the prisoner (Juel, 1990). Clearly it indicated a legal proceeding in progress. And when Jesus made reply that seemed to suggest guilt, the practiced ear of Roman judge caught the suggestion of a criminal confession, and he asked impatiently: “Are you a King then”? This question suggested seriousness and resolution to get at the bottom of the matter with view to a serious judicial determination of the affair (Chandler, 2012). Then there was a defense, or *Excusatio*: in reply to the question of judge, the prisoner answered: “My Kingdom is not of this world” (John 18:36a). And finally, it followed by acquittal, or *Absolutio*: accordingly, he went out to the mob and pronounced a verdict of not guilty. Solemnly raising his hand, he proclaimed the sentence of acquittal. More than any other feature of the case, the verdict of acquittal, “I find in him no fault at all” (John 18:38c) indicated the regularity and solemnity of a judicial proceeding (Chandler, 2012).

Those who support lack of proper procedures in trial of Jesus, these were their main points: a casual perusal of the New Testament narratives left the impression upon the mind of reader that the proceedings against Jesus before Pilate were exceedingly irregular and lacking in all the essential elements of a regular trial. As matter of fact, this impression might be grounded in absolute truth. It may be that the action of Pilate was arbitrary and devoid of all legal forms (Brown, 1994). This possibility was strengthened by the consideration that Jesus was not a Roman citizen and could not; therefore demanded the strict observance of forms of law in his trial (Köstenberger, 2007). In other words, in the case of Jesus, Pilate was not bound to observe strictly rules of the criminal procedure prescribed by Roman law (Garland, 2011). He could, if he saw fit, dispensed with forms of law and disposed of the case either equitably or his whims suggested. Nor was there a right of appeal in such a case, from judgment of the procurator to the emperor at Rome. The decision of the governor against a provincial prisoner was final.

According to the Gospels, the political charges against Jesus were spoken not presented in written forms. According to Roman law, the written charges should be presented and there were no such thing in the trial of Jesus (Della Foreman, 1990). Besides, Jesus’ Roman trial gave no judgment, the customary sentencing formula, *Ibis/abi in crucem* (“You shall mount on the cross” Marcus, 2006) was not pronounced by Pilate, but irregularly he “handed him over” to be crucified by Judeans (Dusenbury, 2021).

Conclusion

Both trials proved that Jesus stood and died for a clear purpose. The appearance of Jesus before the two tribunals brought out the political dimensions of Jesus’ trial and ministry. Jesus was condemned by the two political powers ruling that time, the secular power of Rome and the religious power of the Sanhedrin. Jesus’ trial and death had a political meaning, not in the sense of replacing one power with another power or oppression by other oppression, but in the sense that Jesus’ message had political implications. The “Reign of God” that Jesus proclaimed meant that earthly powers, be it was religiously or secular did not had ultimate power. The reversal of values represented by this rule called the powers to conversion and was subversive (Maniparampil, 2004).

As it had been seen from the very beginning, the trial of Jesus was presented by the all four Gospels. Each Gospel tried to highlight on how the trial of Jesus was conducted by both the Sanhedrin and the Roman authorities. It described on how the irregularities dominated the trial of Jesus in both

parties that were involved in. The trial began with arrest of Jesus in Gethsemane at midnight, and ended with his crucifixion on Golgotha on the afternoon of the same day. It was a double trial, conducted with the jurisdiction of the two most famous systems of jurisprudence known to mankind. In both trials, substantially the right issue was raised. Before the Sanhedrin, the prisoner was charged with blasphemy and convicted.

The proceedings before Pilate, there were a reason to believe, were conducted, in a general way, with due regard to forms of law. But the result was judicial murder, (Dusenbury, 2021) because the judge, after having acquitted Jesus, delivered him and be crucified. “I find in him no fault at all” was the verdict of Pilate. Three times Pilate declared Jesus was innocent in the Gospels of Luke and John (Luke 23:4, 14, 22; John 18:38; 19:4, 6). But this just and righteous sentence was destroyed and obliterated by the following: “And they were instant with loud voices, requiring that he might be crucified. And the voice of them and of the chief priests prevailed. And Pilate gave sentence that it should be as they required (Luke 23:23, 24).

Jesus Christ, the prisoner, had been betrayed to his enemies for thirty pieces of silver; beaten and tortured by his custodians; illegally tried in the highest court of his nation; illegally convicted of blasphemy against the God of his people, a conviction never confirmed in the Roman court. Confirmation failing, the prisoner was charged with treason against the Roman emperor and found not guilty; nevertheless he was “handed over to be crucified” because of inability of the judge failed to stand for the truth.

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